

<http://kmf-publishers.com/jfis/>

RESEARCH ARTICLE

OPEN

Unemployment and Female Labor Force Participation Rate in India

Aamir Ahmad Teeli¹

© The Author 2023

India being a developed economy needs to grow at a rapid pace to lift its population out of poverty and misery. Passing through the stage of demographic dividend India needs to provide gainful employment to its available labor force to be able to reap its benefits. This study aims to examine the puzzling relationship among unemployment rates (overall & youth) and female labor force participation rate. In this paper, we provide evidence of the existence of a negative long-run and short run relationship between female labor force participation rate and unemployment rates (overall & youth). These results suggest discouraged worker effects for females, where higher unemployment rates are associated with lower female labor participation rate. Our analysis reveals the evidence that besides other forces, high unemployment rate is one main driving force behind the puzzle of low female labor force participation and the under-participation trap in India. Also Granger Causality test results reveal the existence of cause and effect relationship among unemployment rate (overall & youth) and FLFPR.

Keywords: India, discouraged workers effect, unemployment rate, FLFPR

Journal of Formal and Informal Sectors (2023), 3(1); DOI: <https://doi.org/>

INTRODUCTION

The economic status of a country is conditioned by various economic indicators prevailing in the economy which include labor market dynamics, capital formation, technological development, economic growth and so on. These economic indicators are the reason for the world being divided in developed, developing and 3rd world countries. Every country tries its best to shape these indicators in such a way that the maximum possible growth and development can be achieved. Among these variables, level of unemployment is a key variable which is closely related to poverty, inequality and economic

growth. Unemployment in a layman's language means a situation in which people are idle and looking for job at prevailing wage rate but are unable to get one. Presence of unemployment is the failure on the part of government and society to provide jobs to the people who are seeking them. Right to employment is part of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Article 23 UN Declaration of Human Rights). Therefore, ensuring employment to all those willing to work is a government's responsibility. The economic and social costs of unemployment and underemployment are

¹Research Scholar Central University of Tamil Nadu, Khiram Bijbehara Anantnag, Kashmir, India.

Email: imamireconomics@gmail.com

Received: 15 October 2022 Revised: 15 November 2022 Accepted: 25 December 2022

Published online: 1 January 2023

staggering; Unemployment causes permanent losses in the potential output of goods and services. Besides it leads to misery and social injustice, particularly in developing countries. But what if there is a decrease in the proportion of people who are seeking jobs and a higher proportion of them are unable to get one. As is happening in case of India, it is a double whammy lower labor force participation rate and higher unemployment rate. For a country like India, which is passing through the stage of demographic dividend, it is most vital that its labor force is gainfully employed so that the fruits of it can be materialized. Improving labor market outcomes more specifically, achieving full, productive, and decent employment is today India's most pressing challenge (*T.S. Papola, 2008*). India's unemployment on an average has remained over 5% since reforms. India's labor markets suffer from much serious inefficiency in major areas. There is Considerable underutilization of labor, which manifests itself in the form of disguised unemployment, existence of appreciably high open unemployment and declining labor force participation rate (*ILO Flagship Report, 2020*). India is facing a drastic fall in the labor force participation rate which was 58.5% in 1993-94, fell down drastically to 54% in 2009-10 and is currently at 51.8%. The situation is worse in female participation rate, India's female labor force participation rate stood very low at 25.22 in 1991. It showed some positive signs till 2005-06 when it reached peak of 26.73 %. Since then it is continuously falling and stood at 21.21% in 2019-20 (*World Bank Figures*). Severely low and decreasing female labor force participation in India is one of the most important problems that Indian policy makers have been facing since long. So this is actually more serious than what is understood via an ordinary investigation. In India the percentage of population seeking employment is falling and the percentage of them unable to get the job is increasing. The youth unemployment rate which was thrice (16.72%) during 1991 stands at about 5 times higher (23.1%) than the overall unemployment rate in 2019-20. India has the youngest population in the world with a median age of

24 years. By 2020, India's average age will be 29, whereas China's would be 37 and Japan's 48 (*Das 2019*). At present, India has the largest young population in the world, with over 65 percent of the population in the working age of 15-59 years. The share is expected to rise till 2035-40 giving India the longest window of opportunity compared to any other country to exploit its demographic dividend (*Kapoor 2019*).

But facing issues on unemployment and labor force participation front, it seems a quite tough task. India is facing serious difficulties in creating employment opportunities for its young and productive labor force. All this will mean clearly missing the opportunity to be counted as a developed economy in the upcoming years. Besides there is established literature that in economies where there is high present unemployment, NAIRU is generally high. Due to high present unemployment, persons who are unemployed lose hope of finding job so it negatively affects willingness to work, work experience and job skills, thereby affecting the NAIRU through affecting the structural and frictional unemployment. One such comment was made by *Prof. Prabhat Patnayak (14 Jun 2019)* in an article written in News Click, quoting that employment status in India is in fact much worse than what is shown in calculations, because there is drastic fall in rural female labor force participation rate between 2011-12 and 2017-18 due to "discouraging effect" which effect the probability of finding a job.

Recent works on unemployment suggest that it is a double-edged sword, which on one side leads to permanent loss of potential output and on the other side effects labor force participation rate via discouraging effect. So changes in prevailing labor market conditions affect the individual participation decisions; these influences are captured by the added worker effect and the discouraged worker effect. Discouraged worker effect works in the view of existence of unemployment in the economy, laborers probability of finding a job goes down which in turn

discourages him to actively look for a job and participate in the labor market. As established unemployment can have a positive side as well via added worker effect, as unemployment family utility function of a family at the time of high unemployment in the economy. The earning losses of one member are expected to be offset by increase in the labor supply of other family members. Net change in labor force participation rate in view of increasing unemployment depends upon the strengths of discouraged worker effect and added worker effect. These effects in turn depend upon the composition and structural aspects of labor force. Many studies in the past have examined this particular puzzle of labor market. **Österholm (2010)** using aggregated and gender-disaggregated data, adopts Johansen cointegration approach as empirical methodology to examine this linkage for Sweden. The author uses both aggregated and gender-specific data, and reaches the conclusion supporting discouraged-worker effect. **Emerson (2011)** finds discouraged-worker effect in the United States. **Kakinaka and Miyamoto (2012)** differ from the two studies by considering age-specific data as well as aggregated and gender-specific data. They conclude discouraged-worker effect for middle-aged and old male groups, and added-worker effect for young male. **Benati (2001)** finds support for the discouraged worker effect for the overall series as well for a number of age–sex disaggregations in the US. **Parker and Skoufias (2004)** found evidence of a significant added worker effect for women in Mexico. This suggests that there is a causal link between unemployment and labor-force participation and the link is puzzling. As mentioned earlier both these variables as such unemployment rate as well as labor force participation rate are cause of serious concern in India. Although many researches had been taken up these issues, but most of them analyzed either of them, none of the study attempted to analyze both of them simultaneously and their mutual association in India. In this regard this study attempts to examine the relationship between the two through the lens of discouraged worker effect and added worker effect.

DATA AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

The study is carried while using secondary data. We use the annual time series data on variables, FLFPR, overall unemployment rate and youth unemployment rate and inflation (CPI) for the period of 1991-2019. The data on study variables is taken from the World Bank database.

We first examined the time series properties of the labor force participation and unemployment rates (overall & youth) using Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) unit root test of **Dickey and Fuller (1979)**. The ADF test has non stationarity under the null hypothesis. Both the levels and the first differences of the series were tested and reported in Table 1. The results of ADF stated that all the variables are stationary at first difference apart from inflation which was found to be stationary at level with 5% level of significance. So null hypothesis was accepted at level but rejected at First difference for the variables of FLFPR, overall unemployment rate and youth unemployment rate while it was accepted at level for inflation rate. Having tested the stationary nature of study variables, the graphical representation is examined.

MODEL

After analyzing the unit root nature of underlying variables, the study is carried while using ARDL auto regressive distributed lag model. ARDL is a statistical technique which is used in modelling the variables are stationary of I(0) OR I(1) or combination of both. In such a situation applying simple cointegration becomes impossible. **Pesaran and Shin (1995)** and **Pesaran et al (1996)** proposed Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach of cointegration or bound procedure for analyzing the long run relationship between the variables which are either level stationary or stationary of first difference or combination of both. The issue of variables having different optimal lags can be dealt easily while using ARDL, which is impossible to take into account in

case of cointegration, which makes ARDL superior to its alternatives, (*Duasa, 2007*).

We examined the relationship among the study variable while using following model framework.

$$FLFPR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FLFPR_{it-1} + \beta_2 Un_{it-1} + \beta_3 YUn_{it-1} + In_{it-1} + E$$

Where FLFPR represents Female labor force participation rate, Un represents overall unemployment rate, Yun represents youth unemployment rate, In represents inflation (CPI) and E is error term or white noise. The short run results of ARDL are presented in table 2.

While analyzing short run relationship in ARDL model we found strong discouraged worker effect for both overall unemployment rate as well as youth unemployment rate. The results concluded that there exists a negative and significant relationship between FLFPR and overall unemployment rate. Same was the case with FLFPR and youth unemployment rate. We found that 4.65% increase in overall unemployment rate leads to 1% decrease in FLFPR. Similarly 1.32% increase in youth unemployment decreases FLFPR by 1%. So the results supported strong discouraged worker effect in the short run. Also we found no significant relationship between inflation and FLFPR.

After estimating short run relationship of FLFPR with overall unemployment rate & youth unemployment rate, it is necessary to test whether overall unemployment rate & youth unemployment rate has long run relationship FLFPR. For this purpose we applied Bounds test. Bound test is an extension of ARDL modelling which is applied in order to know the whether the long run relationship between model variables exists or not. The bounds test is proposed by *Pesaran, shin and smith (2001)*. The technique uses T and F statistic for the said purpose. The long run relationship is said to exist when the value of F-Statistic is greater than upper bond value. if the value of F-Statistic comes to be smaller than lower bound

values then there does not exist any long run relationship and If the F-statistic value comes out to be in between the lower bound and upper bound, result of the inference is inconclusive and depends on whether the underlying variables are I(0) or I(1). Bound test F-Statistic procedure will be invalid in case of any variable is I(2) (*Chigusiwa et al., 2011*). The results of bounds test are presented in table 3.

Based on bounds test results we reject the null hypothesis of no long run relationship at 5% significance level. Hence results confirmed the existence of long run relationship among model variables. After establishing that there exists long run relationship between female labor force participation rate (FLFPR), unemployment (Overall & youth) and inflation rate. We estimated long run relationship. The results of long run relationship are presented in table 4.

Based on long run relationship results we conclude that there exists a negative and significant relationship between, FLFPR and overall unemployment rate in the long run with a coefficient of -20.96. Similarly we found negative and significant relationship among FLFPR and youth unemployment rate with a coefficient of -2.15. Based on the results we found that a higher unemployment rate is associated with a lower Female labor force participation rate. We found significant discouraged workers effect, due to which very large number for women remain out of labor force. During the era of low unemployment, women chose to enter the labor force in large numbers and during the period of high unemployment they choose to stay out of labor force. We found strong discouraged workers effect due to youth unemployment rate where 2.15% increase youth unemployment decreases female labor force participation rate by 1% in the long run. Discouraged workers effect in case of overall unemployment rate although significant but not so strong where we found 20.9% increase in unemployment leads to 1% decrease in female labor force participation rate in the long run. Again we found

no significant effect of inflation on FLFPR in the long run as well.

Also we analyzed the association among study variables by using Granger causality test in order to check whether there exists cause and effect relationship among them. The results of granger causality test are presented table-5. From the results of Granger causality test, the relationships between FLFPR and unemployment rate (overall and youth) were found to be significant at 5% level of significance. While no such relationship was found between FLFPR and inflation (CPI). This concluded that there existed a cause and effect relationship between some study variables where change in unemployment rate both overall as well as youth unemployment rate led to change in female labor force participation rate.

To examine parameter stability of the estimated ARDL model, we employed CUSUM test. From the graphical representation of CUSUM test we found the model to be stable at 5% level of significance. For the purpose of testing the presence of serial correlation we employed Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test. The model was found to be free from serial correlation with P-Value of 0.09 for obs. R-squared. Also we tested for the presence of heteroscedasticity. For the said purpose we used Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test, we found our model free from heteroscedasticity with a P-value of 0.06 for obs. R-squared. Goodness of fit was also justifiable with R-Squared of around 96.

CONCLUSION

The relationship between unemployment and labor force participation has important implications not only for theory but also for empirical modelling and policy in macroeconomics and labor economics. Using ARDL model framework on Indian annual time series data (1991-2019), we found evidence for discouraged workers effect both in the long run as well as short run. The discouraged workers effect was strong for youth unemployment than overall unemployment. Our

results were similar to the *Österholm (2010)* results for Sweden. *Benati (2001)* also found support for the discouraged worker effect for the overall series as well for a number of age–sex dis aggregations in the US. However these results are contradicting with (*Grace and Jaai, 2014*), as they found that the discouraged worker effect does dominate in developed countries, while dominance of the added worker effect in developing countries. *Parker and Skoufias (2004)* had also found evidence of a significant added worker effect for women in Mexico. Investigating the behavior of unemployment rates and their connection to labor force participation rates has improved our understanding of labor market dynamics and its important implications in terms of economic policymaking. One implications of this result is that the policies which are meant to reduce unemployment will prove very helpful in getting rid of the problem of low female labor force participation rate. These findings should be useful to applied researchers and policymakers.

REFERENCES

- Benati, L., 2001. Some empirical evidence on the “DiscouragedWorker” effect. *Econ. Lett.* 70, 387–395.
- Emerson, J. 2011. “Unemployment and Labor Force Participation in the United States.” *Economics Letters* 111 (3): 203–206. doi:10.1016/j.econlet.2011.02.022.
- Kakinaka, M., and H. Miyamoto. 2012. “Unemployment and Labour Force Participation in Japan.” *Applied Economics Letters* 19 (11): 1039–1043. doi:10.1080/13504851.2011.613742
- Kaur, R. (2013). Unemployment on rise in India. Retrieved from [http:// www.mapsofindia.com/my-India/society/unemployment-on-rise-in-India](http://www.mapsofindia.com/my-India/society/unemployment-on-rise-in-India)
- Layard, R., S. J. Nickell, and R. Jackman. 1991. *Unemployment: Macroeconomic Performance and the*

- Labour Market*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Österholm, P. 2010. “Unemployment and Labour-Force Participation in Sweden.” *Economics Letters* 106 (3): 205–208. doi:10.1016/j.econlet.2009.12.002
- Parker, S., Skoufias, E., 2004. The added worker effect over the business cycle: evidence from Mexico. *Appl. Econ. Lett.* 11, 625–630
- Tansel, A., Z. A. Ozdemir, and E. Aksoy. 2016a. “Unemployment and Labour Force Participation in Turkey.” *Applied Economics Letters* 23 (3): 184–187. doi:10.1080/13504851.2015.1064071

Tables and figures.
Table 1 representing ADF results

Variable	Level	First Difference
Overall Unemployment Rate	0.24	-5.49*
Youth Unemployment rate	0.008	-2.99*
FLFPR	-0.61	-6.65*

Notes: *indicates significance at the 5%, ** Indicates significance at the 10%. The lag lengths (given in parentheses) are established using the Akaike Information Criteria.

Table 2 Short Run ARDL results

Variable	coefficient	P-Value
Overall Unemployment Rate	-4.65*	0.012
Youth Unemployment Rate	-1.32*	0.000
Inflation rate	0.038	0.407

Notes: *indicates significance at the 5%, ** Indicates significance at the 10%. The lag lengths are established using the Akaike Information Criteria.

Table 3 ARDL bounds test results

F-statistic	Sig. level	lower bond values	upper bond values
5.428	10%	2.72	3.77
	5%	3.23	4.35
	1%	4.29	5.61

Table 4 Long Run ARDL results

Variable	coefficient	P-Value
Overall Unemployment Rate	-20.96*	0.005
Youth Unemployment Rate	-2.15*	0.000
Inflation (CPI)	0.071	0.441

Notes: *indicates significance at the 5%, ** Indicates significance at the 10%. The lag lengths are established using the Akaike Information Criteria.

Granger Causality Test Results:
Table-5

Direction of causality	No. of lags	F-Statistic	P-Value
Δ Overall Unemployment rate does not granger cause Δ FLFPR	2	9.84	0.004
Δ Youth Unemployment rate does not granger cause Δ FLFPR	2	9.01	0.005
Δ Inflation (CPI)	2	0.88	0.425

